

La Sfera Challenge

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July 17-31, 2020

Welcome to ***La Sfera Challenge II***, a two-week competition pitting international teams of scholars against each other in a race to transcribe multiple copies of one text, Goro Dati's fifteenth-century geographic treatise, *La Sfera*. La Sfera Challenge II will take place among five teams, scheduled between **July 17 and 31, 2020**, and is a reprise of a similar competition that took place between three teams from **May 22-June 5, 2020**.

If you would like to join the challenge, you may email Laura Morreale at lmorreale3@gmail.com, or contact team captains via twitter.

The manuscript copies are housed in five different repositories, and each team will transcribe the copy held in its respective locale according to **challenge guidelines**:

- **Team Yale** will work with a version housed at **Yale Beinecke 946**, team captains Caterina Agostini and Anne McLaughlin;
- **Team Wellcome** will use the manuscript at the **Wellcome Library**, MS 231, team captains Marie Richards and SJ Lahey;
- **Team Spencer** will transcribe the version found **University of Kansas, Kenneth Spencer Research Library, Pryce MS P4**, team captains Laura Ingallinella, Karen Severud Cook, N. Kivilcım Yavuz;
- **Team Vatican** will examine the version in the **Vatican Library**, Vat. Lat. 7612, team captains Carrie Beneš and Winston Black;
- **Team Newberry** will examine the version in the **Newberry Library, VAULT slipcase Ayer MS map 1**, team captains Isabella Magni and Suzanne Karr Schmidt.

The competition is sponsored by the **IIIF Consortium**, **FromThePage**, and **Stanford Libraries**.

You can follow along with the challenge on Twitter at [#LaSferaChallenge2](https://twitter.com/LaSferaChallenge2)

Team Yale

Team Yale is headed by Caterina Agostini and Anne McLaughlin. Watch the **[Team Yale page](#)** for progress updates.

Team Wellcome

Team Wellcome is headed by Marie Richards and S.J. Lahey. **The Team Wellcome page** features updates on participants and progress.

Team Spencer

Team Spencer is headed by Laura Ingallinella, Karen Severud Cook, and N. Kivilcim Yavuz. The **[Team Spencer page](#)** features updates on participants and progress.

Team Vatican

Team Vatican is headed by Carrie Beneš and Winston Black. **[The Team Vatican page](#)** features updates on participants and progress.

Team Newberry

Team Newberry is headed by Isabella Magni and Suzanne Karr Schmidt. **The Team Newberry page** features updates on participants and progress.

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